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REPORT 7

STUDY 3: FORGIVENESS

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Ethical Approval

The reported study was conducted ethically, in accordance with the guidelines of both the University of Delaware and the University of Nottingham's Internal Review Boards.

Forgiving or Punishing: How Born Again Christians Forgive Severe Moral

Transgressions by Politicians

“Forgive as the Lord forgave you” (Colossians 3:13 - second part verse)

Introduction

Political scientists studying political scandals have largely neglected to examine forgiveness, with few exceptions.¹ Although work on voters’ responses to political scandals in day-to-day politics frequently discusses forgiveness (e.g. Saxton & Barnes, 2022; Sonner & Wilcox, 1999; Eisinger, 2000; Muñoz et al., 2016), these studies do not empirically measure forgiveness. Instead, forgiveness is generally assumed when the politician involved in the transgression does not lose significant electoral support and/or remains in office. Assuming the absence of electoral punishment indicates forgiveness is far too simplistic, as there are many reasons why politicians’ immoral behavior might not reduce voter support in polls or the voting booth. Some may simply consider moral transgressions to be normal in politics, and thus discount them. Or, voters may recognize and condemn a transgression but believe it is not relevant to the position. And, of course, there may simply be no other viable choices on the ballot.

Of course, it may be that upon learning about a transgression, some voters are willing to actively forgive the politician. This may be for religious reasons as a tenet of one’s faith, or maybe it’s due to simple politics – forgiving one’s own in-party member while condemning an out-party violator. Forgiveness entails giving up resentment, including the right to retaliate (Strelan et al. 2017) and therefore may reduce the likelihood of electoral punishment. More rigorously studying forgiveness can help to better understand the variation in voters’ responses to politicians’ immoral behavior.

This study aims to answer two research questions. (1) How willing are American voters to forgive politicians involved in moral transgressions? (2) Does partisanship and /or religion condition voters’ willingness to forgive politicians’ immoral behavior? This study focuses on politicians’ moral transgressions, which are often precursors to political scandals, which are “actions or events involving certain kinds of transgressions which become known to others and are sufficiently serious to elicit a public response” (Thompson, 2000: 13).

We conducted a 6x3 between-subjects vignette study with a representative sample of 3000 US voters in which we manipulated the violation of moral principles and the partisanship of the transgressor to examine how voters’ own partisan identity, shared partisan identity between voters and politicians, voters’ religious identity, and the perceived severity of the moral offense explain heterogeneity in voters’ desire for forgiving politicians in response to moral violations.

We find that approximately one third of the American voters thinks that the politician should not be forgiven for his or her misconduct. We find considerable heterogeneity among Americans and their willingness forgive. Their willingness to forgive is dependent on the severity of the crime, whether the politician shares partisanship with the respondents, religiosity and being a born again Christian. The latter group differs from other people in particular their willingness to forgive transgressions that they perceive to be severe.

¹ Some political theorists have considered forgiveness (e.g. Digeser, 1998; Schaap, 2003; Nieuwenburg, 2014) as have some studies of intergroup or interstate transgressions in peace and conflict settings, such as Odak & Čehajic-Clancy (2021), Moeschberger (2005), Wigura (2017) and Blatz & Ross (2011). None of which we are aware have considered forgiveness in the context of voter responses to politicians’ moral behaviour as we do here.

This study contributes to the field examining voters' heterogeneous responses to political scandals, third party forgiveness and ingroup bias in forgiveness in political context, how religion affects forgiveness in politics and intergroup bias in forgiveness.

Third Party Forgiveness of Politicians' Moral Transgressions

Scholars disagree about the definition of forgiveness (Gámiz et al. 2022; Lichtenfeld et al. 2015), in particular, the extent to which not feeling negative emotions or feeling positive emotions towards the transgressor is essential for forgiveness (Exline et al, 2003). Depending on the definition of forgiveness, it consists of two subcomponents, decisional and emotional. Decisional forgiveness refers to the conscious decision to forgive and behave differently toward the transgressor, i.e. to not seek revenge. Emotional forgiveness refers to the replacement of negative emotions, such as anger and hostility, with positive emotions, such as compassion and love towards the transgressor (Lichtenfeld et al., 2005; Exline et al., 2003; Gámiz et al., 2022). The relationship between these two subcomponents of forgiveness remains unclear, for instance, whether one subcomponent precedes the other. Scholars do agree that forgiveness assumes acknowledgement that the transgression was wrong. Thus, forgiveness does not mean ignoring, justifying, or forgetting the transgression, nor does it mean that the transgressor should not be held (legally) accountable or reconciliation *per se* (Exline et al., 2003).

The literature distinguishes between many kinds of forgiveness. A first distinction is made between trait and state forgiveness. Trait forgiveness is “the degree to which a person tends to forgive across time, situations, and relationships” (Davies et al., 2013: 233) and state forgiveness is “a person’s degree of forgiveness of a specific offense”. A second distinction is based on who is forgiving the transgressor, i.e. self-forgiveness, divine forgiveness (forgiveness by God), victim forgiveness, or third-party forgiveness. Not all scholars agree that forgiveness can be studied beyond the dyad of the transgressor and the victim, although the lay use of the word forgiveness actually includes third-party forgiveness (Green et al., 2008). However, some claim that only the harmed party is in a position to forgive and that forgiveness by third parties downplays the harm done to the victim (Exline et al., 2003). Even so, the public generally assumes that third-party forgiveness is possible, as do elites. This assumption is made visible for instance when politicians ask forgiveness for atrocities committed by prior regimes. Third-party forgiveness is less well-studied than other types of forgiveness, such as victim forgiveness, self-forgiveness (Green et al., 2008) or third-party punishment (Green et al., 2003). Surprisingly, research has found that third parties not only perceive moral violations as more severe, but they also are less forgiving than the party actually harmed by the transgression (Green et al., 2008).

Forgiveness serves various purposes and the motivations to forgive differ across people. Forgiveness is generally perceived as beneficial to the grantee, but not always for the transgressor. For instance, when forgiveness is granted too quickly the transgressor does not experience the moral pressure that might cause repentance and forgiveness alone without punishment which might lead to reoffending (Exline et al., 2003). Forgiveness can stem from a personal desire for ease and comfort (Exline et al., 2003). Forgiveness is considered a stress-reducing act as it entails letting go of negative emotions such as anger and guilt. The act of forgiving can also solve the cognitive dissonance people generally experience when an in-group member engages in transgressive behaviour. Forgiveness can also reflect conformity to group norms (Exline et al., 2003), such as a religious group expecting its members to forgive transgressing spouses. Forgiveness makes it possible to restore a relationship with a transgressor over time, a process referred to as reconciliation (Digesser, 1998).

Here, we consider forgiveness as giving up resentment towards the transgressor, including the right of retaliation (Strelan et al. 2017). We are interested in state forgiveness by third parties of politicians' moral transgressions, that is, violations of widely held moral principles. Politician's moral transgressions are often precursors to political scandals which are “actions or events involving certain

kinds of transgressions which become known to others and are sufficiently serious to elicit a public response” (Thompson, 2000:13).

Individual Differences in Forgiveness of Politicians' Immoral Behavior

We know that people respond differently to politicians' immoral behavior, in terms of emotions (Walter & Redlawsk, 2019; 2021); punitive attitudes (Redlawsk & Walter, under review), character evaluations (Anduiza et al., 2013; Bhatti et al., 2013; Walter & Redlawsk, under review) and voting behavior (Costa et al., 2020; Solaz et al., 2019; Solomon et al., 2019.). We do not expect this to be any different for forgiveness. Some people will be more willing to grant a politician forgiveness after a moral violation than other people. The literatures on voters' heterogeneous responses to political scandals and on individual differences in forgiveness, which we derive from the fields of political science, social psychology and religious studies, are instructive. Although people's willingness to forgive has been found to be affected by various victim, transgressor, third party, and transgression characteristics, we focus on two characteristics in particular, namely partisan identity and religious identity. The first has been found to strongly affect people's responses to moral violations by politicians in the study of political scandal and the second has been found to strongly affect people's willingness to forgive in the study of forgiveness.

We know that public responses to politicians' moral violations strongly differ on the basis of partisanship and its strength (e.g. Miller, 1999; Walter & Redlawsk, 2019; Anduiza et al., 2013; Bhatti et al., 2013; Fischle, 2000; Solomon et al., 2019). Especially in the polarized American political system, where other social identities have aligned with party preferences (Mason & Wronski, 2018), partisanship acts as a perceptual screen (Campbell et al., 1960) coloring how partisans view all aspects of politics. Numerous studies have found that partisans are more lenient towards in-party transgressors than out-party transgressors (e.g. Solaz et al. 2019; Walter & Redlawsk, 2019; Solomon et al., 2019), and especially so when people are strong partisans (Walter & Redlawsk, 2021; Craig & Cossette, 2020). The more strongly people identify with a social group, such as a specific group of partisans, the more failures and victories of other group members are considered personal victories and failures (Smith & Mackie, 2016). A group member engaged in moral transgressions can be considered a potential threat to the positive group image and thus to one's self-image. As people wish to create and maintain positive identity they engage (un)consciously in behaviours that can help to do so, such as biased information processing, intergroup bias in perceptions, and ingroup favoritism and outgroup derogation of behaviours (Huddy & Bankert, 2017; Hewstone et al., 2002; Redlawsk, 2002). In the study of forgiveness, people are also found more likely to forgive offenders with whom they are close (Li et al., 2021). Thus, the cognitive dissonance of a transgressing in-group politician and people's positive group and self-image causes great discomfort, in particular to strong partisans, making them the most willing to exhibit in-party bias in granting forgiveness to politicians who morally transgress. Consequently, we formulate the following first set of hypotheses:

Ingroup Forgiveness Hypothesis: Respondents are more willing to forgive in-party transgressors than out-party transgressors

Partisan Strength Hypothesis: The in-party bias in forgiveness is moderated by the strength of respondents' partisan identity.

Research has shown that peoples' religious identity affects moral decision-making and moral behavior (Shariff, 2015). For instance, religious people self-report feeling more sympathy and compassion for others than non-religious people (Łowicki & Zajenkowski, 2021) and self-report more prosocial behavior (Shariff, 2015). They typically do not engage in consequentialist thinking, i.e. that what determines the wrongfulness of an act is not the act itself, but the consequences of the act (Piazza & Sousa, 2017). Although religion has been in decline, it remains important in the US, including US politics. A majority of Americans still identifies as Christian; 64 per cent in 2020 (PEW Research Centre, 2022). Partisan sorting increasingly means Christians identify more as Republicans (Mason & Wronski, 2018). Forgiveness is traditionally perceived to be a moral or religious matter (Gorsuch & Hao, 1993).

Many world religions advocate forgiveness (Rye et al., 2000; Mullet & Azar, 2009). Nevertheless, religions differ in how much they value forgiveness and on the conditions for granting forgiveness (Mullet & Azar, 2009). For example, Christianity generally teaches that forgiveness is unconditional; Judaism does not (Rye et al., 2000). Consequently, most Jews see repentance and atonement as requirements for forgiveness (Levine, 2000) and believe that some transgressions are unforgivable (Cohen et al., 2006). Differences in forgiveness between religious groups are not only due to differences in teachings, but also the culture of the religious group (Cohen et al., 2006). Various studies have found that people's specific religious affiliation affects people's willingness to forgive (Cohen et al., 2006). Most studies find that religious and spiritual people are more willing to forgive (McCullough, 2001; McCullough & Worthington, 1999)

Although forgiveness of others is part of all Christian teachings (Toussaint & Williams, 2008) and for most Christians forgiveness is not conditional (Rye et al., 2000), there are differences between Christian groups in how they see forgiveness (Worthington et al., 2019). Forgiveness is especially emphasized by groups that focus on teachings about the atonement of Jesus Christ and personal conversion, such as Evangelicals (Gorsuch & Hao, 1993; Exline, 2008). Born-again Christians are Christians that consider themselves "saved" or "born again" by seeking and receiving God's forgiveness. Although being saved from sin is traditionally considered central to Evangelical Protestantism, a considerable group of Christians not affiliated with an Evangelical denomination also self-identify as born again (Burge & Lewis, 2018; Schmidt, 2018). People who consider themselves born-again Christians might be more willing to forgive as they received divine forgiveness for all their transgressions enabling a new start.

Several studies argue that forgiveness is not conditional on people's religion, but religiosity. The more (spiritual) and religious people are, the more they value forgiveness and the more willing they are to forgive (Cohen et al., 2006; Toussaint & Williams, 2008; McCullough, 2001; McCullough & Worthington, 1999). One explanation is that more religious members of a group are more likely to practice their teachings and experience the most discomfort when internalized religious values and their behavior is conflicting, including forgiveness (Tsang et al., 2020). Consequently, we formulate the following hypotheses:

Religion Hypothesis: Religious respondents are more likely to forgive politicians for moral transgressions than non-religious respondents

Religiousness Hypothesis: The more religious respondents are the more likely they are willing to forgive morally transgressive politicians

Born Again Christian Hypothesis: Respondents who are born-again Christians are more likely to forgive politicians for moral transgressions than non-born again Christians

We know that how voters' evaluate a politician who commits a moral transgression is dependent on how severe they perceive the transgression (). We know that people differ in how severe they judge the same moral violation (Heffner & Feldman Hall, 2019). Individuals are more willing to forgive offenses that are less serious. The more serious the violation is perceived, the more difficult people find it to forgive (Exline et al., 2003). Some offenses such as crimes against societies and humanity, such as genocide, might be especially difficult to forgive (Exline et al., 2003). To enable forgiveness or deal with cognitive dissonance of in-group members committing moral violations, group members might downplay the severity of the transgression (Otten & Gordijn, 2014; Davies et al., 2022). Therefore it also possible that perceived severity mediates the relationship between exposure to a moral violation and the willingness to forgive. Consequently, we formulate the following hypothesis:

Perceived Severity Hypothesis: Respondents are more willing to forgive moral transgressions that they perceive as less severe.

Data and Method

To examine differences in U.S. partisan voters’ desire to forgive when confronted with politicians’ moral transgressions we conducted a vignette study using a between-subjects experiment in a 6 (5 moral violations and 1 social norm violation) x 3 (levels of partisanship, Republican, Democrat, and none) design embedded in a survey questionnaire. Each respondent was randomly assigned a short vignette describing a fictional, but realistic-sounding scenario in which a politician committed a transgression. Each respondent viewed a single vignette, eliminating the possibility of spill over effects from viewing multiple moral violations. We drew inspiration from the Moral Foundation Theory (MFT) framework to create vignettes representing a range of moral violations. MFT distinguishes five moral principles, namely Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority and Sanctity (Graham et al. 2011).² We added a social norm violation to the moral violations as a potential baseline. In addition, we varied the partisanship of the transgressor (Republican, Democrat, no partisanship) in the vignette. The treatment ensures that results are not limited to a particular type of moral transgression³, but robust for a spectrum of moral violations, and it enables us to test whether voters differ in their intention to forgive in-or out-group transgressors.

The six scenarios are displayed in Table 1. We selected these vignettes from a pre-test of 30 vignettes using a sample of 555 U. S. respondents recruited through Amazon Mechanical Turk. Vignettes were developed by building on Clifford, et al.’s (2015) standardized vignettes which we modified slightly to fit a political context. The vignettes selected out of this set of 30 vignettes best represented each moral principle and social norm while also being perceived by the majority of the respondents as violating that specific moral principle or social norm, while also being understandable and realistic. Full details of the study treatment and the pre-test of the 30 possible vignettes are included in the Supplementary Materials.

Table 1: Six Transgression Vignettes

Violation	Moral Principle	Vignette	Wrong (Mean) Pre-Test	Wrong (Mean) Experiment
Moral	Care	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems	4.25	4.07

² We acknowledge that MFT is contested, for instance in the number of moral foundations (e.g. Iurino and Saucier 2020) and the extent to which the so-called “foundations” are causal first principles (Hatemi, Crabtree, & Smith 2019; Ciuk 2018; Smith et al. 2017). We make use of MFT categories simply to provide a broad range of moral transgressions for testing our hypotheses. Scandals come from different actions by politicians, and there are a wide range of moral principles which may be violated.

³ Our data set only contains one vignette for each moral principle. Consequently, we are unable to separate the specific effect of that particular moral transgression on voters’ willingness to forgive from the generic effect of violating that specific moral principle. Therefore, we refrain from assessing the effect of specific moral principles on votes’ willingness to forgive. Future work should include more than a single vignette for each moral principle.

Moral	Fairness	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs	4.24	3.92
Moral	Loyalty	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician town say the neighbouring town is better	2.45	3.04
Moral	Authority	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police/Chief Constable at a disaster	3.86	3.80
Moral	Sanctity	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician was found having sex with a teenager	4.45	4.61
Social Norm	None	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol/Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag	1.99	2.47

Note: - is a vignette without a partisan label. See supplementary materials for all vignettes pre-tested and selection strategy

Following the pre-test, a survey was conducted between 2 October 2020 and 3 November 2020. We used Qualtrics to administer the survey online to 2977 respondents living in the United States, recruited through Dynata (formerly known as Survey Sampling International). The pre-test and the survey were approved by the institutional review boards of the University of Nottingham and Delaware. The sample provided by Dynata was designed to closely match the American adult population on age, gender, race/ethnicity, income, and region of residence. See Supplementary Materials, Table A2.3 for sample characteristics.

After exposure to the vignette we asked respondents: “When you think about this politician’s behavior, to what extent do you agree with the following statements?” The forgiveness prompt was “The politician should be forgiven for his/her behavior.” This was included with a larger set of retributive and restorative justice statements, all of which were randomly ordered. Respondents were asked to express their agreement on a 5-point scale running from 1=Not at all to 5=Extremely. Mokken scale analysis showed that the item on forgiveness did not scale with any of the restorative and retributive justice items, indicating that the item measures a distinct concept, i.e. forgiveness.⁴ See details in the Supplementary Materials. We decided to recode the dependent variable Forgiveness into a dichotomous variable (0=Not Forgiven;1=Forgiven). We have chosen to do so as this does not change the substantive interpretation of our results, but it does make interpretation of the results easier and it improves our statistical power. In 35.34 percent of the cases the respondents state they are unwilling to forgive the transgressor. The main survey also included stimulus checks, namely whether respondents perceived the act as wrong where 1 indicates Not at all and 5 indicates Extremely. Only 5.7 per cent of the respondents exposed to a moral transgression perceived the transgression not at all wrong. We do not remove these respondents from the dataset, but model the perceived severity. We also asked whether the respondents could recall partisanship of the vignette. Among those who viewed a partisan vignette, 10.15 % of the respondents incorrectly recalled the partisanship of the transgressor. For those who viewed nonpartisan vignettes, 29.44 % incorrectly recalled a partisan label. Best practices suggest removing none of these cases from the dataset, leaving them in the dataset only makes it harder to detect effects, removing them from the dataset makes the sample less representative of the population and affects the balance in the treatment cells (Mutz, 2011). We

⁴ See for this Mokken scale analysis Table A1.1 in the Supplementary Materials. In addition, the spearman rho correlation between the variable Forgiveness and the variable Propensity to Vote, which is measured on a 0-10-point scale (1=Not at all likely;10=Extremely likely) is .351, which indicates a moderate positive relationship between voters’ willingness to forgive and likelihood that they will vote for that politician. The spearman rho correlation between Perceived Likeability of the Politician (1=Unlikeable; 7=Likeable) is .356 and the variable Forgiveness, which indicates a moderate positive relationship between forgiveness and perceived likeability of the candidate.. These correlations indicate that although related these variables measure distinct concepts.

combine all five moral violation types in the analyses, so we are examining what happens when any of these moral violations are seen to occur, without differentiating the moral principles implicated in the vignettes. We conduct sensitivity analyses to ensure that the findings are not driven by a specific vignette. We conducted probit regressions . The models include 2972 observations when all respondents are used, several respondents dropped from the probit regression due to missings on independent variables. When we analyze only partisan responses, the models include 2470 observations In all our models we include various demographic controls including sex, age, education and race. See the Supplementary Materials for full models including the controls.

Initial analyses show that respondents' willingness to forgive politicians' violation moral principles significantly differs from responses to politicians' violating social norms. The change in probability of willing to forgive increases with 13 percentage points when respondents are exposed to a moral violation instead of a social norm violation, see Figure 1. Sensitivity analyses show that these results are not dependent on specific moral vignettes (See the Supplementary Materials.)

Figure 1: The Effect of Moral Transgression on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

Operationalization Independent and Control Variables

Partisanship is measured using the typical 7-point scale, constructed from a series of questions that first ask whether the respondent is a Democrat, Republican, or Independent, and then ask the strength of the party preference. Independents were asked whether they leaned one way or the other. In most analyses we use dummy variables representing Republicans (1=Yes;0=No), Democrats (1=Yes;0=No) and Nonpartisans (1=Yes; 0=No). Nonpartisans are people who do not lean toward one of the two parties. In the regression analyses Republicans are the baseline. **Strength of partisanship** is a folded categorical measure using both questions, where strong partisan=1, weak partisan=2, and leaning partisan=3, with non-leaning independents dropped for the party strength analysis.

The dummy variable **Shared Partisanship** (1=Yes; 0=No) is constructed on the basis of the variable Partisanship and the partisanship label of the transgressor depicted in the vignette. The value 1 indicates that the respondent shares partisanship with the politician portrayed in the vignette with 0 indicating that the respondent does not share partisan identity with the politician portrayed in the vignette.

The variable **Religion** is a categorical variable (1=Yes; 0=No) and indicates whether the respondent self-identifies with a particular religious denomination. The number of Buddhist, Muslim, Hindus surveyed is too small to include as separate religious denominations for subgroup analyses, we include these categories with other religions.

The original composite additive scale **Religiosity** runs from 7 to 40. The scale was constructed after running Mokken scale analysis (Mokken, 2011) on 7 ordinal items that reflect both self-reported intrinsic and extrinsic religiosity. Intrinsic religiosity indicates the extent to which people engage with religion because of the values that they hold and extrinsic religiosity indicates the extent to which people engage with religion as it provides them with external benefits, such as status or community.

The Mokken scale analysis shows that the seven ordinal items constitute a strong uni-dimensional scale with a Homogeneity coefficient of .60. The items measure religiosity, which is people's commitment to religion. The composite additive scale runs from 7 to 40. See Table A1.2 in the Supplementary Materials. For our analyses, we divided the sample into three groups: respondents with scores of 18 and lower have a low level of religiousness; respondents with scores of 19 to 28 have a moderate level of religiousness and respondents with scores of 29 and higher have a high level of religiousness. This results in a distribution of religiosity of 35.5% low, 34.3% moderate, and 30.3% high.

The variable **Born Again Christian** is dichotomous (1=Yes; 0=No). We asked all respondent who identified as Christian, whether they called themselves a born-again Christian, i.e. whether they personally had a conversion experience related to Jesus Christ? We do not equalize born again identity with the Evangelical identity, see for a measurement discussion Burge & Lewis (2018) and Marglis (2022). Our data show that self-identifying born-again Christians can be found among all Christian denominations, including Catholics, Lutherans, Methodists, and Mormons. 27.9 per cent of the sample identifies as born-again Christian, of these born again Christians 51.9 per cent are Republicans, 36.4 percent are Democrats and 11.69 per cent are Independents.

Perceived Severity Moral Transgression measures perceived severity of the moral transgression, by asking respondents to indicate how wrong they consider the behavior of the politician involved. Perceived severity was originally measured on a 5-point scale where 1 indicates Not at all and 5 indicates Extremely. For the purpose of conducting subgroup analyses for different levels of perceived severity of the moral transgression, and considering the small number of observations in the response categories 'Not at all wrong' and 'Not too wrong,' we recoded the variable. We created three dummy variables, Low Perceived Severity (1=Yes; 0=No), Moderate Perceived Severity (1=Yes; 0=No) and High Perceived Severity (1=Yes; 0=No). To construct the dummy variable Low Perceived Severity we combined the response categories 'Not at all wrong' and 'Not too wrong'. To create the dummy variable High Perceived Severity we combined the response categories 'Very wrong' and 'Extremely wrong.'

The control variable Female is a dummy variable (1=Female; 0=Male). The continuous variable Age runs between 18 and 98. Three dummy variables measure respondent's highest educational degree received; No College Degree (1=Yes; 0=No), Bachelors degree (1=Yes; 0=No) and Postgraduate Degree (1=Yes; 0=No). In all models no college degree serves as reference category. Race is measured using a set of five dummy variables; White (1=Yes; 0=No), African American (1=Yes; 0=No), Asian (1=Yes; 0=No) Hispanic (1=Yes; 0=No) and Other (1=Yes; 0=No). The reference category in all models is white. Literature has found some of these demographics to affect forgiveness, women would be more forgiving than men (Toussaint & Williams, 2008) and older people more forgiving than younger people (Toussaint & William, 2008)

Results

This study examines (1) How willing are American voters to forgive politicians involved in moral transgressions? (2) Does partisanship and /or religion condition voters' willingness to forgive politicians' immoral behavior? We first of all look at shared partisanship. Figure 2 shows that respondents are more willing to forgive in-party than out-group politicians involved in moral transgressions, the probability of willing to forgive increases with .8 percentage points when respondents were exposed to an in-party transgressor. We do not find an in-party bias for respondents' willingness to forgive politicians who committed a social norm transgression. We thus find support for the Ingroup Forgiveness Hypothesis.

Figure 2: The Effect of Shared Partisanship on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

Figure 3 shows the results of subgroup analysis, namely the effect of strength of respondents' partisanship on their in-party bias in willingness to forgive politicians involved in a moral transgression. All nonpartisans dropped out of the analysis as we cannot measure partisanship strength for nonpartisans. We hypothesized that the in-party bias in forgiveness is moderated by the strength of respondents' partisan identity. We find that the size of the in-party bias increases with partisanship strength and that only strong partisans are significantly more willing to forgive in party politicians than out party politicians involved in moral misconduct. The in-party bias is border significant for weak partisans. We find that only leaning partisans significantly differ from strong partisans in their willingness to forgive. We find limited support for the Partisan Strength hypothesis.

Figure 3 The Effect of Strength Partisanship on Voters' InParty Bias in Willingness to Forgive

When examining the extent to which religion matters for respondents willingness to forgive transgressing politicians, we first of all, find that people with a religious denomination seem to be more willing to forgive than people without a religious denomination, see Table 4. The difference between religious and non-religious people in their willingness to forgive the transgressor when exposed to a moral transgression is .11 percentage points. We included in our model the effect of shared partisanship as a control variable. We thus find support for the Religion Hypothesis.

Figure 4: The Effect of Religion on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

Although it looks like people who report that they belong to a religious denomination are more likely to forgive politicians engaged in moral transgressions than people who do not belong to a religious denomination, this effect disappears when one enters the variable Religiousness. Similar to other studies we find that whether you belong to a religious denomination does not matter, but the degree that you commit to a religion matters, see Figure 5. The more religious respondents are the more willing they are to forgive a politician for his or her moral misconduct. The probability of forgiving the moral transgressor increases with nine percentage points when respondents score not weak but moderate on religiosity. The probability of forgiving the moral transgressor increases with another 8 percentage points when respondents score strong instead of moderate on religiosity. We thus find support for the Religiousness Hypothesis.

Figure 5: The Effect of Religiousness on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

What is interesting that while controlling for whether respondents consider themselves part of a religion and their degree of religiousness, we still find a significant effect for born again Christianity. Born again Christians are more willing to forgive moral transgressors than people who are not born again Christians. The probability of forgiveness increases with 11 percentage points when respondents see a moral transgression and are born again Christians. We find support for the born again Christian hypothesis we formulated.

Figure 6: The Effect of Born Again Christianity on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

We find that perceived severity has a significant effect on voters' willingness to forgive politicians for their moral transgression. We find only partial evidence that the higher the perceived severity less people are willing to forgive. We cannot reject the Perceived Severity Hypothesis

Figure 7: The Effect of Perceived Severity on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

When we interact between being a born again christian and perceived level of severity of the transgression, we find that the born again christians in particular from other people in their wiligness to fogive politicians for transgressions that are perceid as severely wrong, see Figure 8.

Figure 8: The Effect of Born Again Christians on Willingness to Forgive For Varying Levels of Severity

Conclusion

This is one of the first studies examining American voters' willingness to forgive politicians engaged in moral transgressions outside of the context of interstate or intergroup conflict. On average approximately two thirds of the respondent stated to be willing to forgive a politician for his/her moral transgression. This study shows that not all voters are equally inclined to forgive politicians' immoral behavior. We find that people are more inclined to forgive inparty politicians, that people are more forgiving depending on their level of religiosity, identifying as a born again Christian and perceived severity of the moral transgression. Interestingly enough born-again Christianity matters especially for transgressions that they are perceived as severe. We did find that voters' religious identity played a substantial role in explaining their intention to forgive and should not be overlooked. The findings are interesting, one wonders whether the forgiving nature of born again Christians can explain their continuing support for Donald Trump, who was frequently accused of immoral behavior.

Notwithstanding the contributions of this study, it is not without its limitations. First of all, our dependent variable, forgiveness, was measured using a single item. Although other work measuring third-party forgiveness has also used single item measures, for instance Green et al., 2008, a multi-item measurement would have been better, for instance, the Forgiveness Likelihood Scale (Rye et al., 2001). In addition, this study could not differentiate between unconditional and conditional forgiveness. A follow-on study could provide information about whether the politician apologized, and whether the apologies were accompanied with repentance, atonement, and requests for forgiveness. Several studies have found that people are more likely to forgive when the transgressor has apologized, attempted repentance, atonement, and/or asked for forgiveness. For some people and religious traditions, forgiveness is conditional upon such acts (Watanabe & Laurent, 2020; Green et

al., 2008). Future work could also extend our initial effort here by oversampling respondents of other world religions, which would enable comparisons across religions.

Many studies make use of self-reported measures and thus face the same limitations related to self-reported measures. It is possible that self-reported forgiveness reflects not just people's intention to forgive, but socially desirable responding and/or how people like to perceive themselves. For instance, some Christians might say that they have the intention to forgive as they would like to see themselves as good Christians that are as forgiving as Jesus Christ. Some research has found social desirable responding to be positively associated with religiousness (Sedikides & Gebauer, 2010). In addition, like all surveys that measure intentions, the question remains as to what extent intention translates into actual behaviour. Research indicates that while religious people can express their commitment to forgiveness, in accordance with their religious norms, such expressions do not ensure that they will also act accordingly in concrete circumstances (Brown, Barnes, & Campbell, 2007; Riek & Mania, 2012). Some work finds that Christians might have more forgiving attitudes, they do not have more forgiving behaviour than non-religious people (Hui et al., 2006).

Future work might also want to consider providing information about the transgressor's religious identity to see to what extent a shared religious identity would affect forgiveness, in addition to a shared party identity. The study did not correct for trait forgiveness (Green et al., 2008), as some people have a more forgiving personality than others. The big five traits that are associated with forgiveness are agreeableness and emotional stability (Cullough, 2001).

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